

Interactional behavior studies on surface active ionic liquid lauryl isoquinolinium bromide and anionic polyelectrolytes poly(acrylic acid sodium salt) and poly(4-styrenesulfonic acid-co-maleic acid) sodium salt in aqueous solution[†]

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Abstract : Ionic surfactants have been found to be associating well with polymers but the nonionic surfactant show weaker interactions with most of the polymers. The complex formation between anionic polyelectrolyte poly(acrylic acid sodium salt) [NaPAA] and surface active ionic liquid (SAIL) lauryl isoquinolinium bromide [C_{12} iQuin][Br] in aqueous media has been investigated by surface tension, isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), conductance and the self-assembled structures have been characterized using dynamic light scattering (DLS) and turbidity measurements. Then, a detailed assessment of interactional behavior between the surface active ionic liquid (SAIL) lauryl isoquinolinium bromide ($[C_{12}$ iQuin][Br]) and anionic polyelectrolyte poly(4-styrenesulfonic acid-co-maleic acid) sodium salt [PSS-co-MA] in aqueous media has been studied using different techniques such as surface tension, conductance, dynamic light scattering (DLS) and turbidity to get insight into interactions among $[C_{12}$ iQuin][Br] and polyelectrolyte in the interfacial region. A range of surface parameters and these include surface excess concentration (Γ_{cmc}), surface pressure at the interface (π_{cmc}), minimum area occupied by one molecule of SAIL at air-solvent interface (A_{min}), adsorption efficiency (pC_{20}) and surface tension at critical micelle concentration (cmc) (γ_{cmc}) have been calculated from tensiometric measurements. Further, a series of thermodynamic parameters i.e. standard enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m^0), standard free energy of micellization (ΔG_m^0) and standard entropy of micellization (ΔS_m^0) have been evaluated. Four different stages of transitions, corresponding to the progressive formation of polyelectrolyte-SAIL complex (c_1), critical aggregation concentration (cac), critical saturation concentration (c_s) and critical micelle concentration (cmc) have been observed owing to the strong electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, and the results obtained from various techniques complement each other very well. The size of complexes formed among $[C_{12}$ iQuin][Br] and polyelectrolyte have been characterized using DLS and turbidity measurements.

Keywords :

1. Introduction

An ionic liquid is a salt which exists as liquid below 100°C. The ionic liquids existing as liquid at room temperature are termed as room temperature ionic liquids RTIL's¹. Their physicochemical properties are quite the same as high temperature ionic liquids but their maintenance or handling aspects are

quite distinctive. Surface active ionic liquids are inherently amphiphilic and often called as IL-based surfactants as they possess the combined properties of both of its constituents which are ionic liquid and surfactant². Insight into their interfacial and aggregation properties would provide possibilities for the conventional surfactants and broaden the future ap-

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plications of ILs. The aggregation behavior of ILs in different solutions of additives is of immense interest regarding their applications in fundamental and applied research areas like chemical synthesis, catalysis, electrochemistry, extraction, chromatography, synthesis of new materials, paints and coatings, cosmetics adhesives and pharmaceutical products and many other applications³. Also, these complexes make a strong candidature for good electrolytic systems for high-performance capillary electrophoresis as well^{4,5}. The effort to design a variety of possible SAILs is appealing for the reason that they possess the potential to make an impact in the development and design of the surfactants. The interactions that could possibly exist among polyelectrolytes and surfactants are manifold and are mainly hydrophobic interactions. Depending on the system under investigation, electrostatic interaction or hydrogen bonding can also be dominant. Various interactions can be held accountable for the association phenomena existing in polymer-surfactant systems. The main interactions are hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions. The hydrophobic interactions exist among the hydrophobic tails of polymer, as well as among surfactant molecules. These hydrophobic interactions may also exist among different hydrophobic tails of polymer and surfactant molecules. The electrostatic interactions exist between polymer and surfactant molecules and these may be attractive as well as repulsive in nature depending upon the charges on them. The electrostatic interactions may also exist among the hydrophilic parts within the surfactant molecules. These interactions favor or disrupt the surfactant micellization process. Extensive studies have been carried out upon the systems of polyelectrolyte and oppositely charged surfactant in aqueous solution. There is strong attraction between two oppositely charged species and the binding of surfactant monomers to polyelectrolyte chain starts at a very low surfactant concentration where even pure surfactant doesn't adsorb on the air aqueous interface. The surfactant binding is highly cooperative in these systems which is a consequence of contributions arising from interactions among the adsorbed SAIL molecules, and the formation of micelle-like clusters

adsorbed on the polymer backbone.

Recently, investigations on interaction amid polymer chain and SAIL have been receiving significant attention among researcher due to wide range of potential applications in the field of pharmaceuticals⁶, bioscience, water and soil treatment, oil recovery^{7,8} and nanotechnology⁹. Therefore, the study of the effect of SAIL on aqueous systems comprising polymer is very broad. Recently, our group and Mahajan *et al.*, examined the interaction of anionic polymer sodium polystyrene sulphonate (NaPSS) with cationic surface active ionic liquid based upon imidazolium, $[C_n\text{mim}][\text{Cl}]$ ($n = 10, 12, 14$)¹⁰ and $[C_8\text{mim}][\text{Br}]$ ¹¹. Wei *et al.*¹² have also studied the interactions of aqueous 1-methyl-3-tetradecylimidazolium bromide $[C_{14}\text{mim}][\text{Br}]$ with NaPSS using various methods. It has been observed that the concentration of both surfactant and NaPSS has an effect on the formation of surfactant/polymer complex. The interactions among 1-dodecyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide and sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) have also been studied by Jie *et al.*¹³.

The aggregation behavior of pyridinium-based ionic liquids in aqueous solutions has been discussed in detail in literature¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Isoquinolinium compounds have applications in medical field¹⁸ owing to their biologically active properties. They have been found to exhibit superior antimicrobial activity than similar analogues of pyridinium ILs and quaternary ammonium-based surfactants. Lauryl isoquinolinium bromide $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ is a solid cationic surfactant with melting point (49°C). The literature on the isoquinolinium based ionic liquids¹⁹⁻²⁴ is very limited. The micellization of some N-alkylisoquinolinium based ionic liquids such as butyl isoquinolinium bromide $[C_4\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$, octyl isoquinolinium bromide $[C_8\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ and lauryl isoquinolinium bromide $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ in aqueous solution have been reported by Zhang *et al.*²⁵ using surface tension, electrical conductivity and ¹H NMR measurements. The fact that short chain [$n = 4$ and 8] ILs undergo micellization in aqueous media has been widely accepted. The schematic of present work has been presented into Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

There is no report available on the aggregation behavior of IL [C₁₂iQuin][Br] and anionic polyelectrolytes, NaPAA and PSS-*co*-MA in aqueous media. The aim of the present study is to describe the distinctive nature of thermodynamics of micellization of [C₁₂iQuin][Br] and the micellar structure in aqueous solution of an oppositely charged polyelectrolyte poly(acrylic acid sodium salt) [NaPAA] and poly(4-styrenesulfonic acid-*co*-maleic acid) sodium salt, PSS-*co*-MA by using surface tension, isothermal titration calorimetry, electrical conductivity, dynamic light scattering and turbidity measurements.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials :

1-Bromododecane (> 98%), isoquinoline(> 97%), poly(acrylic acid sodium salt) (NaPAA), and poly(4-

styrenesulfonic acid-*co*-maleic acid) sodium salt (PSS-*co*-MA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Methanol (99%) was bought from Rankem. All aqueous solutions have been prepared using Millipore grade water. The specific conductivity and surface tension of Millipore grade water were measured and were found to be 3 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and 71 mN m^{-1} respectively. The ionic liquid, lauryl isoquinolinium bromide [C₁₂iQuin][Br] has been synthesized and purified into laboratory followed by drying under reduced pressure. ¹H NMR technique was used to verify the purity of [C₁₂iQuin][Br]. The detailed information of chemicals used in the present study has been provided into Table 1.

2.2. Synthesis of lauryl isoquinolinium bromide [C₁₂iQuin][Br] :

A particular amount of both of the reactants i.e. isoquinoline and alkyl bromide were weighed and added to a 250-mL round bottomed flask along with solvent acetonitrile under nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 2 h. Then dichloromethane was added to the crude product obtained after refluxing. Then activated carbon was added to achieve decolourization. Finally, the red coloured thick oil was obtained which was allowed to cool at room temperature. Then several washings with n-hexane were performed in order to achieve recrystallization and remove any unreacted reagents. Later, [C₁₂iQuin][Br] was kept under vacuum for three days to ensure the elimination of any solvent residue. The moisture content was found to be less than 0.02 wt% from Karl-Fischer titration method. The structure of [C₁₂iQuin][Br] was confirmed by analyzing its ¹H NMR spectra.

Table 1. The specification of chemicals

Chemical name	CAS No.	Source	Purity (mass%)
Isoquinoline	119-65-3	Sigma-Aldrich, USA	97%
1-Bromododecane	143-15-7	Sigma-Aldrich, USA	> 98%
Dichloromethane	75-09-2	Sigma-Aldrich, USA	-
Poly(acrylic acid sodium salt)	9003-04-7	Sigma-Aldrich, USA	-
Poly(4-styrenesulfonic acid- <i>co</i> -maleic acid) sodium salt	68037-40-1	Sigma-Aldrich, USA	-

The NMR details of corresponding protons for [C₁₂iQuin][Br] are given below : DMSO-*d*₆ 0.85 (3H, t), 1.22 (20H, m), 4.76 (2H, t), 8.28 (1H, t), 8.40 (1H, t), 8.53 (1H, d), 8.65 (1H, d), 8.89 (1H, d) 10.23 (1H, s).

2.3. Instruments and methods :

All aqueous solutions were prepared using Millipore grade water. A & D Co. Limited electronic balance (Japan, Model GR-202) was used to weigh the chemicals and it had an accuracy of 0.01 mg.

2.3.1. Tensiometry :

Surface tension measurements were performed at 298.15 K using Data Physics, Model DCAT-II automated tensiometer which employed the Wilhelmy plate method. The successive additions of IL into the aqueous polyelectrolyte solution were made by volume. Then the solution was stirred for few minutes with an aim to achieve complete solubilization. After stirring, the solutions were allowed to rest for few minutes to equilibrate. Three readings were noted and they were accurate within $\pm 0.02 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$. The Julabo water thermostat was used in order to control temperature with an uncertainty of 0.01 K.

2.3.2. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) :

The calorimetric titrations of our samples were performed with a MicroCal ITC200 microcalorimeter. The Millipore water was filtered into sample as well as reference cell and maintained at 298.15 K. Then approximately 40 μL of solutions of IL in water and aqueous polyelectrolyte solutions was filled in Hamiltonian syringe which was automatically controlled by the instrument. The surfactant (approx. 2 μL) was added to the sample cell having water or aqueous polyelectrolyte solutions (approx. 200 μL). The solution was stirred continuously at a speed of 500 rpm. The instrument has been provided with software which controlled the parameters such as time and duration between each successive addition. Each addition was accompanied with change in enthalpy and this change at different concentrations was plotted with the help of instruments' origin software.

2.3.3. Conductivity measurements :

A digital conductivity meter CM-183 microprocessor based EC-TDS analyzer with ATC probe was used to measure electrical conductivities in solution. The conductivity cell having electrodes made up of platinum metal and cell constant 1.003 cm^{-1} was purchased from Elico Ltd., India. It was calibrated with aqueous KCl solutions ($0.01\text{--}1.0 \text{ mol kg}^{-1}$) before any experimental measurement was made. The measurements were performed in a double walled flow dilution cell which has been jacket by water and it had an uncertainty of 0.01 K at 298.15 K. Three readings were noted for every particular concentration and finally mean values were considered. The uncertainty in the electrical conductivity measurements was less than 4%.

2.3.4. Dynamic light scattering and turbidimetry :

DLS measurements were carried out with the help of NaBiTecSpectro-Size300 light-scattering apparatus (NaBiTec, Germany) with a He-Ne laser source (633 nm, 4 mW) at 298.15 K. A membrane filter of 0.45 μm pore size was used to filter SAIL-polyelectrolytes solutions of appropriate concentrations into quartz cell which was previously rinsed with filtered water. The measurements were performed at controlled temperature within accuracy of 0.1 K. The laser light from source falls upon the cell containing sample and the scattered light signal was obtained at detector at 90° scattering angle. The instrument had inbuilt CONTIN algorithm which was used to evaluate DLS data.

Turbidimetric measurements of the solutions were performed using (Eutech TN-100) turbidimeter. SAIL-polyelectrolytes solutions of appropriate concentrations were prepared followed by stirring for few minutes. Then the samples were allowed to equilibrate for approximately 5 min and then the measurements were performed.

3. Results and discussion

The complex formation amid [C₁₂iQuin][Br] and NaPAA and PSS-*co*-MA in aqueous media at vari-

ous concentration of polyelectrolytes has been studied using different techniques such as surface tension, isothermal titration calorimetry, conductance, dynamic light scattering and turbidimetry.

3.1. Tensiometry :

In the systems containing polyelectrolyte and surfactant of opposite electrical charges, generally there is an uneven distribution of ions in solution owing to electrostatic interactions leading to enhanced concentration of surfactant ions in the proximity of polyelectrolyte. As the distance from the surface increases, the concentration of ions decreases. The SAIL molecules cooperatively bind to an oppositely charged polyelectrolyte which is a highly favorable phenomenon due to electrostatic stabilization of SAIL micelle. The relative concentration of SAIL molecules at the interface and in the bulk decides the variation in surface tension.

Tensiometric profiles of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in different concentrations of aqueous NaPAA (0, 0.005, 0.010 and 0.025 g/L NaPAA) and PSS-*co*-MA (0, 0.005, 0.0075 and 0.01 g/L PSS-*co*-MA) have been plotted into Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

For pure $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$, the value of surface ten-

Fig. 1. Surface tension of aqueous solutions of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ and NaPAA as a function of added $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in the absence (●) 0 g/L, and presence of different concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (◐) 0.010 g/L, (◑) 0.025 g/L of NaPAA at temperature 298.15 K.

Fig. 2. Surface tension of aqueous solutions of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ and PSS-*co*-MA as a function of added $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in the absence (●) 0 g/L, and presence of different concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (◐) 0.0075 g/L, (◑) 0.01 g/L of PSS-*co*-MA at temperature 298.15 K.

sion gradually decreases with the increase in concentration of SAIL until a knap regime, beyond which surface tension does not decrease further. However, in the presence of polyelectrolytes, many different transitions have been observed at distinct characteristic concentrations where the surface tension changes quite sharply, designated as C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 and cmc which are generally observed in surfactant-polyelectrolyte mixtures²⁶⁻²⁸. With the addition of SAIL, an unexpected fall in surface tension arises at SAIL concentration C_1 due to progressive formation of SAIL-polyelectrolyte complex. After that a hump in surface tension value appears at SAIL concentration C_2 , also called as critical aggregation concentration (cac) because of formation of surface-active SAIL-polyelectrolyte aggregate. Beyond C_2 (cac), a cooperative binding of polyelectrolyte with SAIL molecules is observed due to hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions which results into precipitation which is a commonly observed phenomenon in oppositely charged polyelectrolyte-SAIL systems²⁶ followed by cmc after which the surface tension remains more or less constant. All these characteristic interaction concentrations and surface parameters have been tabulated into Tables 2-5 respectively.

Table 2. The various characteristic interaction concentrations C_1 , C_2 , C_3 and cmc (mmol L^{-1}) observed from surface tension, isothermal titration calorimetry and conductance measurements of $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ in the absence and presence of the polyelectrolyte NaPAA at 298.15 K

[NaPAA] (g/L)		Surface tension	ITC	Conductance
0.000	cmc	5.07	5.15	5.73
0.005	C_1	0.24	-	-
	C_2	1.49	-	-
	C_3	2.97	-	4.36
	cmc	3.83	5.09	5.59
0.010	C_1	0.19	-	-
	C_2	0.87	-	-
	C_3	1.81	-	4.33
	cmc	3.78	4.92	5.23
0.025	C_1	0.25	-	-
	C_2	2.01	-	-
	C_3	3.45	-	4.41
	cmc	4.45	4.98	5.43

Uncertainties are s (conc. of NaPAA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (cmc)_{S.T.} = $\pm 2 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L^{-1}), s (cmc)_{ITC} = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L^{-1}), s (cmc)_{cond.} = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L^{-1}), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

Table 3. The various characteristic interaction concentrations c_1 , cac, c_s and cmc (mmol L^{-1}) observed from tensiometry and conductometry of $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ in the absence and presence of the polyelectrolyte PSS-co-MA at 298.15 K

[PSS-co-MA] (g/L)		Tensiometry	Conductometry
0.0	cmc	5.05	5.22
0.005	c_1	0.45	1.02
	cac	2.23	2.12
	c_s	3.62	-
	cmc	4.73	4.38
0.0075	c_1	0.50	0.63
	cac	2.26	2.34
	c_s	4.13	-
	cmc	5.13	5.08
0.01	c_1	0.50	0.54
	cac	1.97	2.01
	c_s	3.47	-
	cmc	4.18	4.34

Uncertainties are s (conc. of PSS-co-MA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (cmc)_{S.T.} = $\pm 2 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L^{-1}), s (cmc)_{cond.} = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L^{-1}), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

From Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Table 2, Table 3, it is observed that the cmc has decreased with the addition of surfactant to the 0.005 g/L NaPAA as well as PSS-co-MA solution. The addition of polyelectrolyte has been found to decrease the surface tension of the surfactant solution significantly owing to phenomenon called synergistic effect²⁹ resulted by strong attractive interactions among polyelectrolyte and the head groups of oppositely charged SAIL. The effect

is significant at very low concentrations of surfactant where even pure surfactant is incapable of getting adsorbed at the surface of the solution. In this SAIL concentration regime, the surfactant molecules appear to be non-cooperatively binded to the polymer backbone. The cmc value further decreases upon increasing the concentration of polyelectrolyte from 0.005 to 0.01 g/L NaPAA. However, different trend has been noted as we increase the concentration further from 0.01 to 0.025 g/L NaPAA. The cmc value

Table 4. The surface parameters i.e. surface tension at cmc (γ_{cmc}), effective surface tension reduction (π_{cmc}), surface excess (Γ_{max}), minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) and adsorption efficiency (pC_{20}) of $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ and $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ at different NaPAA concentrations

[NaPAA] (g/L)	γ_{cmc} (mN m^{-1})	π_{cmc} (mN m^{-1})	$\Gamma_{\text{max}} \times 10^6$ (mol m^{-2})	A_{min} (nm^2)	pC_{20}
T (298.15 K)					
0.000	30.30	39.72	1.36	1.22	0.03
0.005	32.46	27.55	0.20	8.21	1.35
0.010	32.38	25.62	0.16	9.79	1.36
0.025	33.59	31.41	0.17	9.50	1.20

Uncertainties are s (conc. of NaPAA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (π_{cmc}) = ± 0.2 (mN m^{-1}), s (Γ_{max}) = $\pm 0.03 \times 10^{-6}$ (mol m^{-2}), s (A_{min}) = ± 0.02 (nm^2), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

Table 5. The surface parameters i.e. surface tension at cmc (γ_{cmc}), effective surface tension reduction (π_{cmc}), surface excess (Γ_{max}), minimum area per molecule (A_{min}) and adsorption efficiency (pC_{20}) of $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ and $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ at different PSS-*co*-MA concentrations

[PSS- <i>co</i> -MA] (g/L) T (298.15 K)	γ_{cmc} (mN m ⁻¹)	π_{cmc} (mN m ⁻¹)	$\Gamma_{\text{max}} \times 10^6$ (mol m ⁻²)	A_{min} (nm ²)	pC_{20}
0.0	30.50	31.15	1.36	1.22	0.85
0.005	31.26	31.15	0.13	13.24	1.84
0.0075	31.71	31.61	0.20	8.23	0.26
0.01	31.99	31.88	0.03	52.10	3.13

Uncertainties are s (conc. of PSS-*co*-MA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (π_{cmc}) = ± 0.2 (mM m⁻¹), s (Γ_{max}) = $\pm 0.03 \times 10^{-6}$ (mol m⁻²), s (A_{min}) = ± 0.02 (nm²), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

takes an abrupt increase which is just not a coincidence because same trend has been observed from all other different techniques also. This interesting phenomenon can be accounted to the overriding of hydrophobic interactions over electrostatic attractions between oppositely charged SAIL and polyelectrolyte due to which micellization take place at relatively higher concentration of polyelectrolyte. However, as we increase the concentration of polyelectrolyte from 0.0075 to 0.01 g/L PSS-*co*-MAA solution, the cmc again decreases. However, the cmc value increases upon increasing the concentration of polyelectrolyte from 0.005 to 0.0075 g/L PSS-*co*-MAA solution and the same trend has been noticed by conductance measurements as well. The hydrophobic interactions override over electrostatic attractions between oppositely charged SAIL and polyelectrolyte due to which SAIL monomers have been stabilized leading to micellization at relatively higher concentration of polyelectrolyte. As we increase the concentration of polyelectrolyte from 0.0075 to 0.01 g/L PSS-*co*-MAA solution, the cmc again decreases.

Further, from the tensiometric profile, various surface parameters have been determined by using Gibbs equation such as surface excess concentration (Γ_{cmc}), surface pressure at the interface (π_{cmc}), minimum area at air-solvent interface (A_{min}) covered by single monomer of SAIL and surface tension at (γ_{cmc})³⁰ and their corresponding values have been provided into Table 3.

The surface excess concentration (Γ_{max}) has been

usually calculated through the measurement of adsorption of SAIL in the air-liquid interface obtained by using the following equation³¹ :

$$\frac{d\gamma}{d \ln C_T} = -nRT \Gamma_{\text{max}} \quad (1)$$

where γ is surface tension, R is universal gas constant, T is temperature, n represents number of ions formed in solution and C denotes SAIL's concentration. The minimum area occupied by the SAIL, A_{min} has been calculated from³²

$$A_{\text{min}} = \frac{10^{20}}{N_A \cdot \Gamma_{\text{max}}} \quad (2)$$

where N_A is Avogadro's number. The values of Γ_{max} and A_{min} have been found to follow the opposite trend. For $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]-\text{NaPAA}$ system in aqueous solution of different concentrations of NaPAA, Γ_{max} decreases and A_{min} increases (with an exception of 0.010 g/L NaPAA) signifying that there exists higher concentration of SAIL molecules at the air aqueous interface. The increasing values of A_{min} indicate that packing density increases with increasing the polyelectrolyte concentration at the air-liquid interface. For $[\text{C}_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]-\text{PSS-}co\text{-MAA}$ system in aqueous solution of different concentrations of PSS-*co*-MA, decreases Γ_{max} and A_{min} increases (with an exception of 0.0075 g/L PSS-*co*-MAA) which suggests that there exists higher concentration of SAIL molecules at the air-aqueous interface. The increasing values of A_{min} indicate that packing density in-

creases with increasing the polyelectrolyte concentration at the interface.

pC_{20} is an important surface parameter, which is known as the adsorption efficiency and can be obtained from the equation :

$$pC_{20} = -\log C_{20} \quad (3)$$

Here C_{20} is the SAIL's concentration which decreases the value of γ for pure water by 20 mN m^{-1} . This is the lowest concentration which is required to lead saturation of surface adsorption. The values of pC_{20} have been found to increase with increase in the concentration of NaPAA from 0.005 g/L NaPAA to 0.01 g/L NaPAA for $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]\text{-NaPAA}$ system which indicates that the adsorption efficiency has increased at the air aqueous interface upon increasing the concentration of NaPAA. Although upon increasing the concentration of NaPAA further from 0.01 g/L NaPAA to 0.025 g/L NaPAA, there is a substantial decrease in the pC_{20} values which indicates that the adsorption efficiency has decreased with increase in NaPAA concentration. It suggests that at higher concentration of NaPAA, there is a decrease in the surface activity of SAIL. The values of pC_{20} have been found to increase for $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]\text{-PSS-co-MAA}$ system with the increase in the concentration of PSS-co-MAA (except for 0.0075 g/L PSS-co-MAA) which indicates that the adsorption efficiency has increased at the air-aqueous interface upon increasing the concentration of polyelectrolyte for $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]\text{-PSS-co-MAA}$ system. The substantial decrease in the value of C_{20} at 0.0075 g/L PSS-co-MA, indicates the decrease in the adsorption efficiency with increase in concentration from 0.005 g/L to 0.0075 g/L PSS-co-MA. It suggests that at 0.0075 g/L PSS-co-MA, there is a decrease in the surface activity of SAIL.

Further, a parameter π_{cmc} , the comparative effectiveness of SAIL molecule has been estimated by surface pressure at cmc. That has been calculated using the following equation³² :

$$\pi_{\text{cmc}} = \gamma_0 - \gamma_{\text{max}} \quad (4)$$

Here γ_{cmc} is the surface tension at cmc for a solution of particular concentration and γ_0 is the surface ten-

sion of pure solvent. The values of π_{cmc} have been found to decrease with an increase in the concentration of NaPAA which implies that the efficiency of SAIL in reducing the value of surface tension decreases in the presence of polyelectrolyte. However, it increases at 0.025 g/L NaPAA. In the presence of NaPAA, same trend for both γ_{cmc} and π_{cmc} means that the SAIL's efficiency in reducing the surface tension decreased with increasing polyelectrolyte concentration. Also, overall the values of π_{cmc} have been found to decrease with an increase in the concentration of PSS-co-MA, which implies that the efficiency of SAIL in reducing the value of surface tension decreases in existence of polyelectrolyte. However, for 0.0075 g/L PSS-co-MA, the value of π_{cmc} has decreased which is in accordance with the reason stated above.

3.3. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) :

In order to understand the interactions existing among SAIL and polyelectrolyte, isothermal titration microcalorimetry (ITC) technique has been proved very useful³³ and different parameters like enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m°) and critical micelle concentration can be determined using it. Each surfactant has a characteristic concentration at which micellization occurs and the effect of cosolute could be very striking. In the quest to understand the possible underlying interactions among SAIL-polyelectrolyte system, all calorimetric titration curves of $[C_{12}\text{iQuin}][\text{Br}]$ and NaPAA aqueous solutions have been presented into Fig. 3.

The existence of endothermic peaks (positive values of enthalpies of dilution, ΔH_d) in the ITC curves suggests that the interaction between the SAIL and polymer is controlled by polymer induced micellization. Also, these effects are due to dilution of concentrated micelles of surfactant when they are titrated to aqueous polyelectrolyte solutions. All the dilution enthalpy curves have sigmoidal shape and the cmc can be obtained from the centre point of the nearly perfect sigmoidal curve. The plateau stays flat after cmc in these enthalpograms. The standard enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m°) can be determined

Fig. 3. Enthalpograms of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in the absence (●) 0%, and presence of different concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (◐) 0.010 g/L, (◑) 0.025 g/L of NaPAA at temperature 298.15 K.

by the difference in the heat change amid the first and last knap section at the position of discontinuity. The observed enthalpy change as a function of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ concentration have been plotted into Fig. 3. The enthalpies of micellization for $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in water as well as in different polyelectrolyte concentrations are exothermic (Fig. 3). It becomes less exothermic when the concentration of NaPAA is increased.

It suggests that ΔH_m^o depends upon the hydrophobic interaction between SAIL and polyelectrolyte. However, the addition of SAIL to the polyelectrolyte solutions of all the desired concentration has been found to be an endothermic process for which

electrostatic interaction among the SAIL and polyelectrolyte chains leading to monomeric adsorption can be held accountable. In the absence of NaPAA, a gradual decrease in ΔH_d values from endothermic region towards relatively less endothermic region leading to an overall exothermic effect. At lower concentration of NaPAA i.e. before cmc, hydrophobic region of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ expands and monomers of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ are exposed more to water unite to NaPAA backbone and starts forming aggregates that appears as an exothermic phenomenon. The process continues till the minimum point of curve starts. Further addition of SAIL results in formation of premicelles like aggregates mainly because of electrostatic repulsion between similarly charged head groups $[C_{12}iQuin]^+$ and $[PAA]^+$ dominate over the electrostatic interaction among IL head group and counter ions which leads to an increased change in magnitude of endothermic enthalpy changes for micelle formation of IL i.e. at 0.025 g/L; when similar change has been observed but smaller in magnitude. It is expected that electrostatic repulsions between the charged groups are prominent than its interactions with monomers of SAIL present at lower concentration which leads to an insertion of $[C_{12}iQuin]^+$ difficult into the already present micelles.

It has been observed from the surface tension measurements that the cmc values for the SAIL-polyelectrolyte aqueous solutions are lower than the cmc of pure aqueous solutions of SAIL. At the lower concentrations, the cmc decreases but when the concentration becomes appreciably higher, a slight in-

Table 6. The thermodynamic parameters for the binding and micellization of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ at different NaPAA concentrations

[NaPAA] (g/L)	cmc (Cond.) (mmol L ⁻¹)	α (Cond.)	ΔG_m^o (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_m^o (ITC) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$T\Delta S_m^o$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
T (298.15 K)					
0.000	5.73	0.62	-31.67	-6.39	25.28
0.005	5.59	0.58	-33.65	-5.97	27.68
0.010	5.23	0.45	-35.77	-5.84	29.94
0.025	5.43	0.54	-34.07	-5.88	28.20

Uncertainties are s (conc. of NaPAA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (cmc)_{cond.} = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L⁻¹), s (ΔG_m^o) = ± 0.02 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (ΔH_m^o) = ± 0.01 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (ΔS_m^o) = ± 0.02 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

Table 7. The values of critical micelle concentration (cmc), degree of dissociation (α), free energy of micellization (ΔG_m^0), enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m^0) and entropy of micellization (ΔS_m^0) of aqueous $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ solutions in different concentrations of PSS-co-MA at different temperatures

PSS-co-MA (g/L)	cmc (mM)	α	(ΔH_m^0) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	(ΔG_m^0) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	(ΔS_m^0) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
T = 298.15 K					
0.0	5.22	0.375	-12.13	-37.35	84.58
0.005	4.38	0.377	-10.02	-38.01	93.88
0.0075	5.08	0.386	-5.29	-37.21	107.05
0.01	4.36	0.372	-10.72	-38.14	91.99
T = 308.15 K					
0.0	5.39	0.387	-12.24	-38.18	84.18
0.005	4.71	0.390	-10.59	-38.67	91.12
0.0075	4.92	0.399	-6.31	-38.27	103.74
0.01	4.47	0.383	-10.21	-39.05	93.60
T = 318.15 K					
0.0	5.63	0.396	-13.04	-39.02	81.66
0.005	4.91	0.397	-15.82	-39.57	74.67
0.0075	4.85	0.410	-5.93	-39.30	104.90
0.01	4.58	0.393	-11.99	-39.98	87.98

Uncertainties are s (conc. of PSS-co-MA) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ g/L, s (cmc)_{cond.} = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ (mol L⁻¹), s (ΔG_m^0) = ± 0.02 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (ΔH_m^0) = ± 0.01 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (ΔS_m^0) = ± 0.02 (kJ mol⁻¹), s (T) = $\pm 1 \times 10^{-2}$ K, s (p) = ± 2 kPa.

crease has been noticed as observed from the tensiometric measurements. The cmc values obtained from ITC have been found to be higher than cmc values obtained from the tensiometric measurements. It is due to slow process of micellization of SAIL-polyelectrolyte system because in tensiometric measurements cmc is considered as the point where no more surfactant molecule can be adsorbed at the air-water interface while isothermal titration calorimeter, cmc corresponds to onset of micelle formation. Here, we have also observed that the cmc first decreases upon increasing the concentration upto 0.01 g/L NaPAA. Later, cmc decreases upon increasing the concentration of NaPAA, that is, upto 0.025 g/L NaPAA. The values of enthalpies of micellization (ΔH_m^0) obtained here have been further used to calculate various thermodynamic parameters of micellization in the up next section.

3.3. Conductance measurements :

The experimental electrical conductivities at temperature 298.15 K for solutions of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in aqueous solution of NaPAA in different concentra-

tions of NaPAA and PSS-co-MA) and have been presented into Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively as a function of SAIL's concentration.

Fig. 4. Specific conductance (κ) of aqueous $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ solutions in the absence (●) 0%, and presence of different concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (●) 0.010 g/L, (●) 0.025 g/L of NaPAA at temperature 298.15 K.

Fig. 5. Specific conductance (κ) of aqueous $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ solutions in the presence of different concentrations of PSS-co-MA (a) 0 g/L, (b) 0.005 g/L, (c) 0.0075 g/L, and (d) 0.01 g/L PSS-co-MA at different temperatures (\bullet) 288.15 K, (\circ) 298.15 K, (\square) 308.15 K.

The values of cmc and various parameters have been listed into Tables 2 and 3. In the electrical conductivity versus concentration plots, two straight lines have been obtained. These lines have been found to have different slopes and micelle formation has been accounted for it. The cmc value has been assigned to the point of intersection of these two tangential lines. The conductometric profiles of the systems studied shows a decrease in the values of cmc of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ after the addition of polyelectrolyte NaPAA. It means that the electrostatic attractive interaction among the charged head groups of both SAIL and polyelectrolyte are dominant over the hydrophobic interactions existing among the hydrophobic tails of both the interacting components. These electrostatic interactions facilitate early micelle formation. From Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it is clear that the cmc has initially decreased upon addition of surfactant to lower concentrations of polyelectrolyte solution because the phenomena of micelle formation has taken place. The repulsion among head groups reduces at micellar surface because of electrostatic interactions and the cmc has been approached to a much lower concentration than in case of pure SAIL system. However, the cmc has been delayed at higher

concentration of polyelectrolyte because the hydrophobic interactions come into play and stabilize individual surfactants monomers delaying the micellar process for $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ -NaPAA system. For $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ -PSS-co-MA system, the steric interactions among the bulky head groups of SAIL prevail and stabilization of individual surfactant monomers via hydrophobic interactions can be accounted for this phenomenon. However, further increasing the concentration to 0.01 g/L PSS-co-MA, again a decrease in cmc has been observed which indicates the early stabilization of SAIL.

The ratio of slopes of pre and post micellar region in the conductance versus concentration profile^{34–37} provides the degree of counter-ion dissociation (α). In the conductivity profiles, a break has been observed in high SAIL's concentration region which is around C_2 in the surface tension trend followed by cmc. The redissolution leading to restricted movement of counter ions can be hold accountable for the slow increase in conductance post cmc. Finally, on further addition of SAIL, more and more SAIL molecules adsorb on the backbone of polyelectrolyte leading to enhanced positive charge on the polyelectrolyte. If the concentration of polyelectrolyte is increased, values of cmc of systems under investigation decrease except at appreciable higher concentration for the reason mentioned in the previous section.

Various thermodynamic parameters of micellization have been calculated for SAIL-polyelectrolyte system of current interest using the temperature dependence of cmc. The standard Gibbs free energy (ΔG_m^0) of micellization for the SAIL-polyelectrolyte all the systems have been calculated using equation³⁸ :

$$\Delta G_m^0 = (2 - \alpha)RT \ln X_{cmc} \quad (5)$$

where X_{cmc} is cmc that has been obtained from electrical conductivity vs concentration plots and has been expressed in mole fraction.

Further, entropies of micellization, (ΔS_m^0) have been calculated using values obtained from the ITC curve from the following equation³⁸ :

$$\Delta S_m^\circ = \frac{\Delta H_m^\circ - \Delta G_m^\circ}{T} \quad (6)$$

By using the provided equations, the thermodynamic variables have been calculated and reported into Table 6 and Table 7. The changes in different parameters have been observed with change in polyelectrolyte concentration and they collectively point towards some important phenomenon occurring into SAIL-polyelectrolyte aqueous solutions. The values of $T\Delta S_m^\circ$ have been found positive while ΔH_m° being negative for all the concentrations of NaPAA indicating that micellization process has been co-driven by entropy and enthalpy. The micellization process is exothermic. The aliphatic chains of SAIL molecules have gone under hydrophobic solvation because of enclosing of SAIL molecules in between the much ordered structure of water molecules as compared to free water molecules. It distorts the hydrophobic hydration through micelle formation followed by higher entropic state of the system as a whole. It contributes to the formation of micelle^{39,40}. With the increase in polyelectrolyte concentration, ΔH_m° decreases pointing that less heat has been evolved with increase in polyelectrolyte concentration. Also, it is inferred that the enthalpy change contribution is lesser than the entropy driven phenomenon during micellization process at all concentrations. Overall, the values of ΔH_m° become more negative upon increasing the concentration of polyelectrolyte indicating that the process has become more spontaneous. The efficiency of SAIL has been improved in the presence of polyelectrolyte.

3.4. Dynamic light scattering and turbiditometry :

Dynamic light scattering measurements have been performed to determine the hydrodynamic size, geometrical shape, and type of self-assembled aggregates of $[C_{12}i\text{Quin}][\text{Br}]$ in aqueous medium in the presence of 0.01 g/L NaPAA and 0.01 g/L PSS-co-MA solution to know how the size distribution varies with change in concentration. The hydrodynamic radii, R_h , of the self-assembled structures measured from DLS have been presented into Figs. 6 and 7 respectively.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the hydrodynamic diameter R_h for the 0.010 g/L NaPAA solution in the presence of different $[C_{12}i\text{Quin}][\text{Br}]$ concentrations at temperature 298.15 K.

Fig. 7. Distribution of the hydrodynamic diameter R_h for 0.01 g/L PSS-co-MA solution in the presence of different $[C_{12}i\text{Quin}][\text{Br}]$ concentrations at temperature 298.15 K.

Upon the addition of SAIL in the concentration range below C_1 , SAIL monomers just start to bind to the chains of polymer because of electrostatic attraction as observed in both the electrical conductivities and tensiometric measurements at C_1 and two different peaks are witnessed in DLS measurements. The two different peaks show the existence of both the polyelectrolyte monomer and multimers. Initially the second peak is small and narrow which shows that the formation of multimers has just started. Later the second peak becomes broader showing the existence of polyelectrolyte and SAIL complex. The first peak with smaller hydrodynamic radii corresponds to

soluble complex formed between SAIL and polyelectrolyte in the diluted equilibrium solution while the latter with larger hydrodynamic radii has been allocated to the insoluble aggregates of SAIL and polyelectrolyte. If the surfactant addition is continued further, there is a decrease in R_h leading to the coiling up of structure of polyelectrolyte- $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ complex as a result of which the hydrophobic part of the SAIL approach each other. This creates aggregates of bounded SAIL molecules to the polyelectrolyte chain. Finally, for $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$, at a concentration exceeding cmc, hydrodynamic radii shrinks due to existing polyelectrolyte-SAIL complex. An attempt has also been made to get insight into the size of complexes formed among $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ and polyelectrolyte in the concentration range of interest using turbidimetry. The change in turbidity of SAIL in different concentration of aqueous polyelectrolyte solutions has been depicted into Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The turbidity increases with increase in SAIL's concentration, and then precipitation is observed. At surfactant concentrations exceeding cac, the turbidity sharply decreases and becomes roughly constant due to redissolution of precipitates.

Fig. 8. Turbidimetric profiles of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in the presence of different profiles concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (○) 0.010 g/L, (▲) 0.025 g/L of NaPAA at temperature 298.15 K.

Fig. 9. Turbidimetric profiles of $[C_{12}iQuin][Br]$ in the presence of different profiles concentrations (●) 0.005 g/L, (○) 0.0075 g/L, (▲) 0.01 g/L of PSS-co-MA at temperature 298.15 K.

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